

STRENGTH OF CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES CONTAINING PIN LOADED HOLES

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ABSTRACT

A method based upon the maximum hole deformation is proposed to predict the tensile strength of carbon/epoxy laminates containing one or two pin loaded holes. The method is based on the expected damage state of the laminate at fracture. A linear finite element analysis is used together with a degradation model over a characteristic zone ahead each bolt hole. The fracture loads obtained with the proposed method are compared to experimental failure loads presented in the literature.

Keywords: composites, joints, carbon epoxy, fracture.

1. INTRODUCTION

Complex composite structures usually require the joining of sub-structures. The joints may be either bonded or bolted. Bolted joints are normally heavier than bonded joints. However, bonded joints are very susceptible to failure by delamination. Therefore, bolted joints are considered to be more reliable under fatigue loading and have been extensively used in aircraft manufacturing.

The design of bolted joints involves several parameters. The geometry is defined by the number of rows and their relative position, the hole size, the pitch of the joint and the edge distance. The designer must also define the material(s), the number of layers and their orientation, and the type of bolt to be used. The joint may fail by shear, tension or bearing. Failures by shear or tension are catastrophic. However if proper values of the design parameters are used, these failure modes can be avoided and failure by bearing, that is not catastrophic, will occur.

The analysis of a composite bolted joint is a very complex problem. It is a contact problem between a number of flexible bolts and the composite laminate. Obviously, a theoretical or experimental analysis of an entire joint would have a prohibitive cost. A conservative simplification is the analysis of a specimen with a width equal to the pitch of the joint including a representative number of bolts and the same edge distance. Usually a double lap configuration is assumed so that three dimensional effects due to bending may be neglected.

In this work, a method based upon the maximum hole deformation is proposed to predict the tensile strength of carbon/epoxy laminates containing one or two pin loaded holes. The method requires a two dimensional finite element analysis of the joint to estimate the hole deformation. However, if a linear model is used, the computed hole deformations are in average two times smaller than the experimental values [1]. This discrepancy is mainly due to the laminate degradation during loading. Therefore, a realistic prediction of the failure load requires a non-linear finite element analysis of the laminate.

A simplified method is developed to obtain the laminate failure load from a linear analysis. The method is based on the expected damage state of the laminate at fracture.

The proposed method was originally devised to predict the bearing strength of a composite laminate with a single pin loaded hole [1]. The present work shows that it can be successfully extended to the case of laminates containing two pin loaded holes in series yielding reasonable estimates of the fracture stress even for failure modes other than bearing.

The fracture loads obtained with the proposed method are compared to the experimental failure loads of carbon/epoxy laminates containing one or two pin loaded holes presented in ref. [2].

2. FRACTURE CRITERIA

Several criteria have been proposed to predict the strength of composite bolted joints with the simplifications previously described. These criteria can be classified in two categories: (a) criteria based on a non-linear analysis that takes into account the progressive damage of the material [3], and (b) criteria that predict the strength of the joint based on the stress distribution obtained from a linear analysis of the problem [4,5].

The progressive damage theories [3] give a better representation of the actual mechanical behavior of the joint. However, these criteria demand a high computational effort and do not produce more accurate estimates of the joint strength than theories based on linear analysis.

The criteria based on linear stress analysis are simpler but require the use of characteristic parameters difficult to evaluate experimentally. Agarwal [4] proposed that failure by bearing occurs when the average of the compressive stress over a certain characteristic length ahead of the bolt reaches the unnotched strength of the laminate. Similar criteria are proposed for failures by shear and tension.

Chang [5] assumed that fracture of the joint occurs when a failure index based on the Yamada-Sun criterion is equal to 1.0 over a characteristic curve defined in terms of two characteristic lengths of the material. The position of the point with highest failure index indicates the failure mode. The author comments that the method is highly sensitive to the shape of the characteristic curve.

Santacreu and Almeida [6] tested several carbon/epoxy bolted joints with different thickness and lamina orientations. They measured the deformation of the hole as a function of the applied load and observed a highly non-linear behavior in the contact region between the bolt and the laminate. A typical load vs hole deformation curve is shown in figure 1. The experimental results showed that there is significant degradation of the material even for the linear portion of the curve. The authors defined the limit load P_{lim} as the load corresponding to a 4% deformation of the hole as determined by the procedure described in ASTM Standard D953. They observed that, for all laminates tested, these values are in close agreement.

They also submitted at least one specimen of each type to 10^6 fatigue cycles with stress ratio $R=0.1$ and maximum load value corresponding to a hole deformation of 4%, that is, P_{lim} . After that, the static strength of all joints were measured. The measured residual strength indicated that there is no significant loss in the strength of the joint after the fatigue loading.

Santacreu and Almeida [6] used the observations above to suggest that a carbon/epoxy bolted joint should not be designed based on its fracture load but rather on its limit load P_{lim} without the need for a safety factor. The experimental results supported their proposal but the linear finite element analysis performed by the authors resulted in hole deformations that, in the average, were two times smaller than the experimental values.

Gonçalves and Almeida [1] studied the causes of the discrepancy between the linear finite element analysis and the experimental results for the hole deformations presented in [4]. A non-linear finite element model assuming rigid pin and zero friction between the laminate and the bolt was found to yield good correlation with the experimental values of the hole deformation for several types of laminates. In such analysis the degradation model proposed in [3] was used combined with the Tsai-Wu failure criterion.

The model used in [1] can be used to estimate the load corresponding to a 4% deformation of the hole, that is the limit load P_{lim} as suggested in [6]. However, this method requires a very large computational effort compared to the linear model. The results of the non-linear analysis for several different types of laminates indicated that the degraded zone at failure of the joint by bearing was very similar to the characteristic curve used in reference [5]. This observation is consistent with the hypothesis used in [5] that failure occurs when the stress over a characteristic curve reaches a critical value. Moreover, a post mortem analysis of the specimens tested in [6] revealed that degradation of the laminate was evident over a region approximately equal to the one limited by the characteristic curve.

Figure 2 shows a typical comparison between the degraded zone obtained by the non-linear analysis performed in [1] and the characteristic curve proposed in [5]. From these facts Gonçalves and Almeida [1] concluded that an accurate estimate of P_{lim} could be easily obtained if the degraded zone at failure were assumed to be equal to the zone encompassed by the characteristic curve. A single analysis sufficed to yield good approximation to the actual deformation of the hole. The method was extended to predict the ultimate load and presented good correlation to the experimental results presented in [4] and [6].

In the present work the method proposed in [1] is extended to obtain the ultimate load of joints containing two holes in series. The method is applied as proposed in [1] and the assumed degraded zone is considered for the two bolt holes. An ultimate deformation of 3.6% used in the prediction of the theoretical values was found to yield good correlation when compared to the experimental results presented in [2]. This ultimate deformation is used also for the model with the two holes in series.

Figure 1. Typical curve for the load vs deformation of the hole

Figure 2. Finite element model used in [1] showing the characteristic curve and the degraded zone

3. RESULTS

The proposed method was applied to the joints analyzed in reference [2]. The geometry of the problem is shown in figure 3, where D is the hole diameter, H is the laminate thickness, W is the specimen width, E is the edge distance, and G is the distance between hole centers.

The specimens were manufactured with Fiberite T300/1034-C graphite/epoxy. The material properties used in the analysis are given in reference [2]. Four different ply orientations were used: $[(0/90)]_S$, $[(\pm 45)]_S$, $[(0/\pm 45/90)]_S$, $[(90/\pm 60/\pm 30)]_S$. The results for one and two pin loaded holes in series are presented in table 1.

The comparisons between the experimental data and the results of the model are performed in terms of the bearing strength PB . For laminates with a single loaded hole or with two holes in series, the bearing strength is expressed as $PB = P/DH$, where P is the failure load and DH represents the cross sectional area of the hole.

The results shown in table 1 were obtained from a finite element model using MSC/NASTRAN. The two dimensional model was implemented using elements type CQUAD4. A degraded zone was assumed ahead each bolt hole. They are limited by the characteristic curve proposed by Chang[2]:

$$r_c(\theta) = \frac{d}{2} + r_{ot} + (r_{oc} - r_{ot}) \cos(\theta), \quad -\frac{\pi}{2} < \theta < \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (1)$$

where θ is an angle measured from the symmetry line of the specimen, r_c is the radial distance from the characteristic curve to the center of the hole, d is the hole diameter, and r_{ot} and r_{oc} are characteristic distances that depend on the material. In this work, it is assumed $r_{oc} = 3.048$ mm and $r_{ot} = 1.092$ mm as suggested in ref [2] for carbon/epoxy laminates.

Within the degraded zones the material is assumed to have degraded elastic properties as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1^{\text{DEG}} &= 0.25 E_1 \\ E_2^{\text{DEG}} &= 0.25 E_2 \\ G_{12}^{\text{DEG}} &= 0.25 G_{12} \\ \nu_{12} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

where the upper script indicate the degraded property.

Table 1 presents the predicted strength of the joints tested in ref [2]. These values are compared to the experimental and theoretical results obtained by Chang [2].

Figure 3. Geometry of the problem

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The proposed method was originally devised to predict the bearing strength of a composite laminate with a single pin loaded hole [1]. The present work shows that it can be successfully extended to the cases of laminates containing two pin loaded holes. Moreover, the data in table 1 indicate that even for failure modes other than bearing, i.e. shear-out and tension, the present method also correlates reasonably well with the experimental results.

It must be remarked that the use of a second row of bolts penalizes the cost and weight of the joint but may not lead to a significant increase on its strength. A judicious choice of the geometrical parameters and lamina orientations is required to obtain a non-catastrophic type of failure and an improvement on the strength of the joint. It is recommended that the pitch of the joint and edge distance are chosen such that $W/D \geq 5$, and $E/D \geq 3$.

The proposed theory presented good correlation with the experimental results for all cases analyzed. The method is simple to use and does not require a large computational effort. Therefore, the proposed theory can be used for the preliminary design of mechanically fastened composite joints with one or two rows of bolts.

Table 1 Comparison between the experimental results and predicted values

Geometry	Laminate	Experimental results				Present method		Ref. (2)	
		Single hole		Two holes		Single hole	Two holes	Single hole	Two holes
		Fracture load (MPa) x 10	Failure mode	Fracture load (MPa) x 10	Failure mode	Fracture load (MPa) x 10			
W/D = 5	[(0/90) ₆] _s	63	Shearout	106	Shearout	56	96	40	54
E/D = 3	[(±45) ₆] _s	69	Tension	75	Tension	56	85	46	41
G/D = 3	[(0/±45/90) ₃] _s	81	Bearing	116	Tension	83	135	81	104
D=1/4"	[(90 ₂ /±60/±30) ₂] _s	69	Bearing	83	Tension	70	110	61	41
W/D = 10/3	[(0/90) ₆] _s	43	Shearout	95	Tension	54	93	43	63
E/D = 2	[(±45) ₆] _s	47	Tension	55	Tension	45	63	34	33
G/D = 10/3	[(0/±45/90) ₆] _s	86	Tension	83	Tension	75	113	81	88
D=3/16"	[(90 ₂ /±60/±30) ₂] _s	57	Tension	69	Tension	63	90	57	64

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